

THE ROMAN CATHOLIC LEGACY
Human Society Affected by Actions of Religion
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Although I have used the expression Roman Catholic (RC); this is not meant to be a focus on one particular belief system in the present century. The term RC evolved in the early centuries of the first millennium. Those who were part of the belief system which carried the name, installed numerous concepts into the minds of many generations of European nations over many centuries. As happens with all such systems the RC system was the origin of numerous other systems (departures) which arose from the same basic concepts promulgated by the RC system. This paper is not about the legacy of the written words (doctrine) used by the RC systems; these are all subject to many doubts; as I will explain later. This paper is about the actions of the RC system and any of those other belief systems, which also carried out similar actions. These actions are not subject to doubt as they are part of the fully documented records of historians. Hence take the term “RC” to include others and the term “legacy” to be from historic records of actions not doctrine.

We should not ignore that this legacy, a double edged sword, has been transported across the entire globe through the dual agencies of colonisation and evangelism.

This paper is not based on theory or other sources, but personal experience of hearing and living the words of four Holy Men during my life. One in London in the UK; two in Istanbul, Turkey and the fourth in Vrindavan, UP, India.

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The Basis of This Document

This document is based on the effect of teaching the same as that of Jesus. It is certain that Jesus lived a life with peace, equanimity and mental stability in every minute of every day. How do I know that? Because I cannot believe that He lived a life which would be less than that which I live myself from having both heard and lived the teachings given to me by the four people mentioned above (in the UK, Turkey & India); identical to Jesus’ teachings. This life of one who is less perfect than Jesus is described in the Yoga Vasishtha IV:61 :-

“Those beings in whom purity is preponderant with just a slight impurity, are ever happy, enlightened and do not grieve or despair. They are unselfish and desireless. They are at peace within themselves and they do not abandon this

peace even in the worst calamities. They love all, and look upon all with equal vision. They do not drown in the ocean of sorrow.”

After many decades of practise, this is the outcome of culturing a life with the wisdom in the teaching received. That teaching is in essence the same as that which has been reported that Jesus gave to the people around Him. His one aim was to give people a better life every day in the present.

Heaven is that kind of life described above, here and now. Not some place elsewhere at a different time or in a different place. Hell is a life without those three qualities mentioned above. Hell is here and now; it is the condition of the human mind when it is filled and controlled with thoughts and desires about pleasures, wealth and importance or fame. These kinds of thoughts ultimately produce stress, concern or other mental disturbance. These things are the main subjects which conceal heaven within the mind. This is Hell. Hence such was the compassionate nature of Jesus that He gave guidance in the form of teaching and how to put His teaching into everyday life. He did not promise immediate salvation but instead recommended a changed way of everyday life; as mentioned above, which anyone can find with the right kind of effort sustained over many decades; which in itself would lead to liberation from bondage.

Saul of Tarsus

So much of the RC way of understanding Jesus hinges on the man called Paul (Saul); that it must needs be that I settle the status of this man before proceeding with this document. From the experience and teaching received from the four men mentioned above I will outline why I could not accept Paul as a holy spiritual teacher in any way whatsoever. He may have been an experienced preacher and knowledgeable about spiritual matters, but this does not qualify him to be the instigator of a true way to discover the Creator in human life and hence be at peace every minute of every day. There are many qualities which he does not display in his writings and his actions; qualities which all truly holy people show in abundance. One of them is equanimity; another is the knowledge that the human soul is an eternal part of the Creator and only requires the removal of the ignorance which prevents us from seeing that. This ignorance can take a whole human life to remove; and much effort from the one who seeks union with the Creator; of whom Jesus was a representative on earth. There is no instant relief as promoted by Saul in his salvation promotion talk.

Any person who claims to have been saved through mere faith in Jesus, as suggested by Saul of Tarsus, needs to simply review their everyday life and honestly ask:- **‘Is it filled with peace and equanimity every minute of every day?’** Or does it have ups and downs and stress and worry at any time about any person or any event in life? If it is the latter, then that person is not saved; it is only an imagination based on hope and the effect of the cult like promise in Saul’s way of zealous language. The euphoria which is not long lasting..

Such is the basic ignorance of the majority of the human race about truly spiritual matters that Paul was adopted by the Romans, mainly because Paul

had such a large following; and the Romans wanted to please as many as possible with their new combined religion. Also that Saul's idea of instant salvation is less arduous than the effort required to put Jesus' teaching into practise; hence more attractive. Saul never heard Jesus' teachings. Whatever he says about getting teaching direct from Jesus is only his word, it has never been corroborated independently. It is mainly to convince others to follow him.

Authority to Act

In the UK many people set themselves up as builders for works on houses. There is no regulation of this activity; hence many people employ a 'so called' builder and do not get good quality work done on their houses. But to practise in the capacity as an architect or structural engineer is regulated to some extent. To qualify as a structural engineer I had to pass through many years of specific and recognised, engineering education, then apply for registration into a professionally recognised institution. As a member I could offer services as a structural engineer. Customers could be fairly sure that I knew what I was doing and would **not** provide a solution which would fail. This professional recognition was my "**authority to act**". When it comes to the religious or spiritual subject, in the UK there is no regulation of who is qualified to provide a service. As far as I know the same applies in most civilised countries. Hence religious types seek an "**authority**" to gain followers; to convince potential followers.

At the time of Jesus there was a man called Jesus Bar Abbas. It is likely he chose that name to cash in on the reputation of Jesus of Nazareth. Jesus Bar Abbas preached religious matters and had a large following. The Roman gospel compilers had the idea that no other one should carry the name of Jesus, so that part was later removed from Jesus Bar Abbas and his name was written as simply Barrabas. 'Bar' in Aramaic means "son of" and 'Abbas' means "Father or God". He was a rival to Jesus and in addition Bar Abbas appeared as an antagonist to the Roman occupation of the area. Although he was arrested for sedition, he was also preaching under his name which meant 'Jesus son of God' this was his "**authority to act**"; he was not arrested for doing that. Hence it is clear that at Jesus' time there was no regulation about who could set him/herself up as a preacher of religious matters.

The above subject was well known to all those who chose to become preachers of religious subjects during Jesus' time. Hence if they wished to prove authenticity of their organisation they would need to seek a recognised or established authority. Saul of Tarsus was well aware of this situation. He was actually a reformer of the Jewish religion. It was his opinion that it needed modernisation in his time. After he had an experience that Jesus of Nazareth could work miracles, and that He was well known for that, Saul decided that he could use the name of Jesus to put a stamp of authority onto his preaching; this was his "**authority to act.**" This is clear, as he uses this method in all his letters which have been gathered and erroneously placed in the Bible. This method of using Jesus' name would overcome the risk of being seen as one of the many

fake teachers like Jesus Bar Abbas; such people have always been around in large numbers. There are in this century at least 100 fake holy men in India for every truly realised holy man; it is the same in the USA. Fame and fortune is their aim. Saul of Tarsus was clearly of this type. He was very successful because modern Christianity is mainly based on the teachings of Saul.

Now transplant the above situation into the 4th Century AD when the Romans accepted the various groups who were preaching religious subjects; and decided to make one religion by combining all of them; and to naturally include aspects of the established Pagan way of worship; so that all Roman citizens would feel happy to follow the new religion. In addition to the Pagans, there were many groups at that time; the Jews and followers of Saul of Tarsus (Paul) and various Christian groups. Also we can guess there were many other fake religious teachers who were not included, due to having a small number of followers. All societies across the world have many of these types.

The main subject for these new 'Roman Bible' compilers would be to establish the "**authority to act**" otherwise a new religion enforced by the Roman state would not be acceptable to the population at large. To do this they clearly had a team of people scan all the scriptures, which had been chosen for the new religion, to find an "**authority to act**".

The Catholic church claimed its authority to act in the name of Jesus based on one verse in the New Testament. Matthew chpt. 16 verse 18; which was conveniently interpreted as:- "*--- that thou art Peter, and upon this rock I will build my church ---*" But in the closing part of the chapter it is also written, verse 20; "*Then charged he his disciples that they should tell no man that he was Jesus the Christ.*" This last statement does not indicate that Jesus wished others to hear about His teachings. The original word translated as "Church" was "ekklesia", it meant only a small gathering of people. Our word "ecclesiastic" which can mean priest comes from that. But the original meaning did not relate to religious or holy matters; it was translated with an idea to support the formation of something which Jesus did not instigate, which was when the word "ekklesia" meaning church, first appeared in the Bible. It was used to mean a building like a Roman temple or Jewish synagogue where many people would meet under the control of another authoritarian person. This was part of the Roman plan for a new combined, state controlled religion.

This interpretation to start a "church" is based on the earliest known text of the Bible dated between 325 AD and 350 AD. Three centuries after Jesus time; and known as the Codex Vaticanus. If we ask how did this document appear at that time? The answer is that all previous documents were collected by the Romans and scribes were commissioned to prepare a book of scripture to support the new religion being created by the Romans in the Vatican; authorised by Emperor Constantine (306 - 327 AD). After that, all previous manuscripts were destroyed. What was it they had to hide? The discovery in the 20th Century of original documents which pre-date the Roman involvement with Jesus' teach-

ings, is the answer; explained below under the heading “Spreading Jesus’ Teaching”, the Dead Sea Scrolls and the Nag Hamadi scriptures. This will show that the Romans made up their “**authority to act**” to suit themselves.

One such book discovered at Nag Hamadi is called the Secret Gospel of John. Scholars place this book as relating to when Jesus returned to Palestine from Damascus eighteen months after the crucifixion. He returned to meet His disciples who were having some problems when discussing His teachings. After that He returned to Damascus to continue His Journey to the King of Nisibis; near modern day Turkey. These facts recorded at the time of Jesus are some of what the Romans destroyed, because they do not suit the false picture that Jesus died on the cross and never lived outside of Palestine. There is another whole history of Jesus’ life which has been rejected and suppressed by the RC church, because it does not suit the false story which they created, mainly built on the words of Saul of Tarsus, who never met Jesus. There is today a house where Jesus stayed in Damascus called “The resting place of Jesus”.

Doubts About Doctrine

The RC system was established on written words, called doctrine, recorded by people who were not followers of the man who spoke those words. Written words cannot be relied on as being truly authentic in terms of their deeper meanings or intentions of their originator. Let me explain. Teaching, which is of a profound nature relating to the invisible and intangible subject of communication with the Creator of the world we live in, has three basic parts:-

1. The first part is the veracity of the words of the teacher. This will depend on the clarity or depth of his or her connection with the Creator; and the command of the language which the teacher has for the purpose of communicating concepts. This also means sufficient words in the language used, which convey the subject matter. The supreme language of spiritual matters is Sanskrit, which has nearly one million unique words. Many are specifically about the spiritual subject. Jesus knew this language from being in India. The Jewish language has less than half that number of words. Hence some concepts would be difficult to express. Whereas this language, English, has more than double the number of words as the Jewish language. Subtle concepts need the right understanding, with the right words; else misunderstandings may arise.

2. The next part relates to the one who hears the words spoken. This also depends on that person’s original inner purpose in wishing to hear the words. This means, does he or she wish to improve or purify their own life, such that they may be able to share in the connection with the Creator in the same way the teacher has done? [*John 1: 12-13 “But as many as received him, to them he gave the power to become the sons of God,”*] In our context this means reflecting on the teaching. In this situation the correct understanding of the meanings in the words may have value. Any other person, who hears the original words from idle curiosity or

without a real intention to purify his or her life, may never come close to the inner meanings contained in the teaching. Such words are not meant for the non-seeker of Truth; i.e. the one not prepared to make effort.

3. The third part is the most important in that it requires the teaching to be put into practise in the life of the hearer; the one who has the good intentions mentioned above. After persistent practise of the teaching, such a person will know it's true meaning; and can be regarded as a follower of the teacher. All others who only like to hear the words are not followers, if they do not put them into daily practise. The mental delight in hearing spiritual language will not itself change the established habits of the reader or listener. Action and effort are needed to change habits.

A fourth part, "allegory", is not always relevant but is often the cause of false beliefs or misunderstandings due to the allegory not being fully or correctly understood.

Hence it should be clear that any person who writes down the teachings of a person who had a closeness to the Creator, could not easily use language which carries the true intentions of the teacher, unless the writer had (a) heard those words from the teacher in person and (b) fully understood what the meaning was; and (c) had practised their content and had understood what was required to be done.

It is for the above reasons I use the word "**doubts**" in connection with doctrine. Truly there are many doubts especially when profound teaching moves across language boundaries and the effects of time, added to misunderstandings of allegory etc. and the intentions of those who copied or compiled the doctrine.

Let us look at an example of the above. There are twelve people who have been named as followers or apostles of Jesus. When He gave them safety advice related to teaching others, it is reported that He said, "*And whoever will not receive you nor hear your words, when you depart from that house or city, shake off the dust from your feet.*" (Matt. 10:14). This advice carries with it at least three important elements, (A)"Not receive - nor hear." and (B)"Depart from that house or city." (C)"Shake off the dust-"; which means never to return to that place, because the people are not pure enough to make any use of the teachings. This was **safety** advice given by Jesus, because He knew from experience that people can become violent when you tell them things, which mean that their lives are in need of improvement. And the teaching can only be given by a teacher who is alive; not one who has been stoned to death or murdered another way. Hence it is important to stay alive. If those twelve had fully comprehended these reasons for Jesus' advice; and had established it as a practise in their lives; they would never have been in danger of being murdered.

Of the twelve people listed as apostles only John was reported to have died a natural death. All the others were murdered by the people they were trying to teach. Hence we should hold in question whether all of these eleven people were truly followers of Jesus; as it is clear they did not take the precaution of

leaving a place (or refusing to go) where the people were hostile. We presume they heard the advice mentioned above, but they clearly did not have the habit of following that advice for their own safety; which means they were not true followers. Also we should note that they did not live long enough to establish anything which would continue Jesus' teachings. Their deaths have been referred to as 'martyrdom'. This is merely a systematic way of covering up mistakes by ignorant religious people. Jesus never made giving up the life of the physical body as a way of putting His teaching into practise. This would obviously be counter-productive.

The above example should clarify what is meant by item 3 above related to putting the teaching into practise. It may be that some people believe that writing Jesus' teaching into books and reading it out every day or every week to a gathering of people is putting the teaching into practise. It should be clear to all readers that such behaviour is not what was intended by Jesus. More about this subject of 'gathering of people' later.

Therefore I conclude that the formation of a book called the Bible by the groups who lived in Rome during those early centuries, is filled with doubts. This is because they were so remote from the time of Jesus and from the possibility of really understanding His teachings. Few people know that the original manuscripts had no spaces between words, and no verses or numbers. Adding these makes it seem like nothing is missing. A clever move on the part of the compilers to cover up their editing of the original texts.

Those who translated it and those who chose some parts and omitted other parts, could not claim to be true followers of Jesus. This also applies to most of those who followed the system which they set up. This paper will make this very clear as I unfold the ignorant legacy they have left us with; showing that, point by point, they have not really come close to being followers of Jesus by their actions; which speak louder than words. If they have not followed Jesus' teaching they themselves are not to be followed.

Yet there are many individuals who have perceived the above description of true or false follower, and have designed their life truly in accordance with what was left of Jesus' teachings after the Romans had done their editing.

Spreading Jesus' Teaching

As will become clear later there is no doubt that the RC organisation has been at the centre of spreading the teachings of Jesus. But was this their main purpose? The evidence shows us that it was not. The original bibles were only in Latin; a language not accessible to the ordinary person. Also there were no bibles available to the general population until mass printing of books became possible in the 15th century. So before that time we cannot say that the RC organisation planned to make Jesus' teaching directly available to all. The first printed bible was in 1455 in Germany and it was in Latin. It was nearly 100 years later the first English copy became available. So eventually we can say that the RC organisation was inadvertently responsible for ordinary people to be

able to read Jesus' teachings. But this was not their original aim. They actually corrupted the original texts to suit their ideas of what religion should be.

If we seriously examine the origins of the RC organisation we see it started with a mixture of groups of people who followed different kinds of life, in the religious way. Judaism was the main system of belief in the early centuries. Yet it had suffered centuries of altered and corrupted ways; ending in more of a political / people control system, than a way to discover the Creator in life. Jews had very strict rules about almost every community subject. Jesus was Jewish by birth; and many people who knew of him, not first-hand, assumed that He was a teacher of a form of Judaism. Judaism was very important then.

Saul of Tarsus was more attached to Judaism than Jesus' teaching. Saul (who later went by the name of Paul) was a reformer of Judaism. This comes across very clearly if the letters he wrote (or dictated) are read as being Jewish documents, not Christian. I say this because really the only connection with Jesus in Saul's letters is the call to, "**In the name of Jesus Christ.**" Adding Jesus' name into the text of his writings does not make it truly Jesus' teaching. If we openly read Saul's writings they are clearly Saul's teachings not those of Jesus; and they are closer to Judaism than the teachings of Jesus. Saul called his followers "Christian Jews". This was simply cashing in on the name of Jesus; and it shows they were really Jews, not followers of Jesus. The followers of Saul were one of the main groups who formed the original RC organisation setup. Was this really Christianity?

Edmund Szekely the author of the 1937 book, "The Gospel of Peace of Jesus Christ", taken from ancient manuscripts discovered to have been hidden away within the Vatican in Rome, commented in the Forward to that book :-

"And although his (Jesus') words, as we know them today in the New Testament, have been terribly mutilated and deformed, they nevertheless have conquered half of humanity and the whole of the civilisation of the West. This fact proves the eternal vitality of the Master's words, and their supreme incomparable value.

"It is a heavy responsibility to proclaim the present New Testament, which is the basis of all Christian Churches, as *deformed* and *falsified*, but there is no higher religion than the truth."

This statement is a mixture of opposing sentiments. On the one hand he is stating that Jesus' words have benefitted humanity. On the other hand he is saying that the teachings have been changed in some way. Is it possible to know about these changes which he claims? Surely this would be important if a person wanted to be a follower of Jesus and His teachings.

And a little nearer to our times in 1952 the following comment was made by Khwaja Nazir Ahmad in his book "Jesus in Heaven on Earth"

"If a true account of the life of Jesus had been handed down to us, there would have been no Christianity as it is known to us today. The needs of the church, changing with the growth of Christology, had eliminated most of the authentic

but inconvenient details; and introduced into the Gospels certain incidents and even whole episodes, which were more appealing than historical facts. What should have happened was made to happen; what should have been said, was represented as having been said."

More evidence that the Romans edited the texts to suit themselves.

Robert Eisenman studied the Dead Sea scrolls, discovered ten or more years after Edmund Szekely published the statement above. Robert wrote in the introduction to "The Dead Sea Scrolls Uncovered", published in 1992, the following :-

"So what in effect do we have in these manuscripts? Probably nothing less than a picture of the movement from which Christianity sprang in Palestine. But there is more - if we take into consideration the Messianic nature of the texts as we delineate it in this book, and allied concepts such as 'Righteousness', 'Piety', 'Justification', 'works', 'the poor', 'Mysteries', what we have is a picture of what Christianity *actually was* in Palestine. The reader, however, probably will not be able to recognise it because it will seem virtually *the opposite* of the Christianity with which he or she is familiar."

The above people are unbiased scholars who were seeking the truth of history; they were not taken-in by the rhetoric of the religious types. Similar comments have been made in relation to the Nag Hammadi scriptures, discovered in Egypt in 1945. There are many other gospels in those scriptures which show us what the RC compilers destroyed. We must note that as recorded by Josephus the historian of the time, there was no following of Jesus in Palestine in the first century. He does not mention any new religion arising alongside Judaism. Maybe due to the fact that the so called apostles, all but one, were murdered, there were no reliable witnesses to start up anything called Christianity.

If we gather all the facts together and are honest, we may discover that we have been seriously misguided by the RC system from the early centuries of their organisation. The gospel manuscripts they copied were end of 1st century.

Interesting to note that Edmund Szekely's comment was made about one hundred years after the official end of the RC inquisition courts. If he had made such research and comments in earlier centuries he would most likely have suffered execution. As would other similar commentators. We now live in an age where we are allowed to think for ourselves. Hence we are able to point out where the RC organisation has deceived us; without the risk of persecution.

Perhaps if we list the things which we know Jesus did not teach as His way, it may open a path to seeing what the RC church has really set up :-

1. Jesus did not teach or begin an organisation with bishops and priests etc. for people to gather in large numbers to worship the Creator. See the item, Matthew Chpt 6 vv 5&6 under the section on "Gathering people -" later on.
2. There is no teaching of Jesus which re-establishes the concept of removing sin through blood sacrifice. This was Judaic and was re-started by Saul in his letters. The blood and flesh of Christ are part of RC ritual. This is not Jesus teaching. He taught leading a good life to avoid sin.

3. There is no emphasis in Jesus teachings or focus on the execution of spiritual leaders on a wooden cross as being of any spiritual significance. This is an RC invention; a Pagan ritual for signifying a new Spring life. Not taught by Jesus.
4. There is no teaching of Jesus that the birth of a spiritual teacher has any more importance than any other time of his life. This is an RC adoption of an ancient Pagan ritual which focussed on the change point at which, in the northern hemisphere, the setting of the sun reaches its lowest point and begins a new year in relation to the length of sunlight each day. This happens around 21st December and for three days it remains the same until it begins to change on the 24th December. Hence the new birth of the year begins on 25th December; a Pagan ritual with the birth of Jesus superimposed onto it.
5. Also Jesus did not teach that people only needed faith in Himself to get salvation for their souls i.e. the instant salvation promoted by Saul of Tarsus. Jesus' parables are all about developing noble attitudes and establishing a life with good and honest principles. Not seeking wealth and importance. Developing and establishing these attitudes can take many decades of a person's life. It is not instant.

The Sustained Follower

The teachings should be read many times, not only once then placed on the bookshelf. What is the reason for this? Firstly, there are usually several levels of meaning in the words of holy people. These will show themselves on subsequent readings. Secondly, and as important as the above, is the effect of the passage of time. It may be that a true follower understands the teacher's words and makes them part of life's daily pattern. But time will bring about change. Slowly every decade of our lives unfolds new ideas, new aims and a new outlook. All this change will be reflected in the way our mind controls our life. The human mind is as changeable as the weather; in fact more so. We can never trust the mind to be consistent. Hence as each phase of life unfolds, previously established ways can become eroded or rejected. Here lies the need to sustain practise correctly.

Where the true seeker has been previously established in the practise of the teaching, this may become seen by the mind as without value. It is necessary to make attempts to sustain the way of life. Hence in addition to making the follower's life in accordance with the teachings, reading them many times and continuing to reflect on their meaning will increase the chance of sustaining their effect on life and opening the deeper levels of meaning. Also each day is a life in itself. The meanings of holy teaching must be remembered, reflected upon and put to practise every day of our lives, if we wish to improve.

One important side of this is finding one or two others who share the same approach to the teachings. Regular discussion with such people is of immense value in sustaining the practise over many decades. When I say one or two, I mean no more. Jesus supported this idea when He said, "*For where two or three are gathered together in My name, I am there among them.*" *Matt. 18:20*. Larger numbers bring in the risk of dissent and personality problems. Two or

three can more easily find harmony and agreement. Especially since the spirit or presence of Jesus will most certainly come amongst them; Jesus keeping His promise to those who become true followers. Two or three is not the modern day church idea of large gatherings.

This subject is behind the story (or parable) which Jesus gave about building on rock in preference to sand. Matt. 7:24 to 27. Really the analogy is not about building a house, but about building a life based on Jesus' teachings. He said, "*--who hears these words of mine and does them --*" the matters I have referred to above. But there is a second level to this building on rock. It is the two matters referred to above. Reading many times and finding one or two others who share the same ways. This is all about forming a strong framework or foundation for sustaining the pattern of life. It can take decades.

The Denigration of Women

This is a long section, but it is important as it contains the key to many other parts of this document. Read it slowly and carefully. Some of you have never heard this before.

In the reported teaching of Jesus recorded in the Gospel of Luke chapter 10 verse 42, Jesus stated. "*And one thing is necessary, and Mary has chosen the best part which shall not be taken from her. ---*". This relates to when she remained at the feet of Jesus and only wanted to hear His teachings, despite her sister Martha asking her to help with the domestic tasks. This follows my description of a true follower mentioned above; hearing the teaching from the lips of the teacher, with the only purpose to live it in life.

Yet there is more to this. Jesus clearly did not see any difference between the male gender and the female. Otherwise He would not have exalted her choice in that way - "**the best part**". Here He was setting the standard of equality of gender.

There is another example, the lady called Mary Magdalena. She is mentioned more times in the reported gospels than the male followers of Jesus; and she was accepted as being close to Jesus all the time He taught in Samaria. She was never sidelined or made to be inferior to any of the males connected with Jesus' mission. These facts can only mean that Jesus did not in any way support the denigration of women, and this approach was naturally in His followers. Those writers who knew this about Jesus could not give preference to men over women when recording the remembered teachings. This should be clear to any follower of Jesus who lives as described in the previous section. Yet this evidence did not influence later views about the female gender held by the so called church fathers.

Now we need to open up a difficult side to the roots of the religious denigration of the female gender. Difficult, because scripture does not mean directly what it says in words. It mostly uses allegory or parable. Generally people do not fully appreciate this; the Old Testament text has been misunderstood.

As I have said above, few people really understand the teachings of truly holy persons. It is partly the reason that Jesus used parables. Storeys or parables contain a specific subject which focuses the mind of the reader. Contained within the narrative is a theme used to illustrate a spiritual directive or advice. The reader needs to unravel the story and discover the inside meaning. During this process the reader is more likely to arrive close to the intended directive, than if it were spoken in difficult to follow language, subject to misunderstanding or misinterpretation. This partly gets around the risk of false understanding of spiritual teachings, which use human language.

Let us be clear, holy teaching is never about another place or another time; but about the purity of our thoughts, words and actions today. There is only today, there is no other day during which we can practise the wisdom of the teaching. The planet revolves on an axis like movement. One side faces the sun the other side is in shadow. The day is a constant face with sunlight on it. Living on one side of the globe we pass in and out of this one day; yet we give it a different name and number each time we pass in and out. It is the same day that Jesus walked here on this planet. There is only this one day.

With this concept in mind we should not create silly ideas about time and space from the words of holy scripture. There was no mysterious day in the past when human beings were created. They are being created during this one day in the present. The scripture is about today – this one day is when it all happens. The Adam and Eve story is not about the past. It is about what is happening now; it is clearly a literary device or allegory.

The Adam and Eve story has become a well established misunderstanding. Over thousands of years, moving between many cultures and many languages it has been falsely related to the creation of two human bodies at some time in a non-existent past. We cannot leave out the possibility that the basic misunderstanding was many centuries ago and has affected revisions or re-renderings of the original text. Well established misunderstandings which survive many centuries are almost impossible to extract from the minds of people who have believed the misunderstood text for many generations. We must therefore cut it to the bone to get at the truth. To anyone who knows what the basic spiritual difficulty is in human life, they will see that the Adam and Eve story was actually a description of the way in which all human beings are made inside; both male and female. Not about their physical bodies. Holy scripture does not need to explain the physical body to us. It is not about the past either. It is about what is happening here and now. As said above there is only this one day.

It goes without saying that all human societies know that the physical strength of a female is much lower than a male. But deep spiritual texts are not about the physical body, they are about the inner and less easy to observe aspects of being human. The description of the human in two parts is about one part which is strong and the other part which is weak. For the above reason called “man” and “woman” in the scripture.

The weak part is the individual ego or changeable aspect. The strong part is the True Self (or soul) of each human being which is unchangeable; hence stable and strong. Changeability is a weakness in this subject. The other part of the Adam and Eve parable is the heaven and hell aspect along with the serpent or tempter. These are again ways of depicting difficult to follow concepts of human life, but using tangible parts of the world. They are here now; not something in another place or another time. I repeat, there is only today.

Heaven is nothing less than a state of peace and happiness which is within the human experience. Hell is the converse state of stress and worry about all matters in our lives. These two states are within our daily lives in this present moment; in this one day. Jesus gave a hint about this inferring that the kingdom of heaven is within us. Not in some other place or another time. If this is true then so is hell. The serpent is the inner voice of our own mental thoughts and desires, which continually diverts our attention from the real world in front of us. The serpent was used in the analogy because snakes usually inject poison into the lives of others. All these parts of the spiritual analogy have been erroneously made into physical ideas outside of the human experience and at another time and place which do not exist. This was not the intention of the one who originated the scripture. Truly holy people know there is only today.

There is no being referred to as the Devil; it is our miscreant mind which is always chasing desire after desire. It has always been difficult and maybe counter-productive, to tell people direct to their face that they have an evil mind and they need to reform their lives. Remember what happened to Jesus' disciples who tried to teach people; also to Jesus Himself. The serpent and Satan are literary devices not physical entities. Evil is nothing more than mental desires.

Ancient languages are not easily accessible to us. But there are two ancient words which have been retained in Sanskrit relating to the basic nature of all humans. These are **Atman** and **Jiva**. Atman is the embodied portion of the Creator, the individual soul; this part cannot make direct contact with the world around; hence it can never be affected by what happens in life; it only watches or observes. It is the pure consciousness in us. Jiva is an aspect or modification of Atman, which we may also call the individual ego (personality or character) it is with this part we make contact with the world; it is the agent or helper in this respect; Jiva is the one who is affected by what happens. This is the basic two part design of the inner human being; it does not relate to the physical body. That is another thing entirely. Being non-physical Atman is difficult to study; analogy is a necessary helper. Hence the Adam and Eve analogy.

From the above we can easily see that the translators of the Hebrew sounds adam and ihawwah became Adam and Eva; and that they are close enough to Atman and Jiva. The story is clearly about two parts of all humans, not about two human beings. Atman is the strength of man as it is not affected by anything which happens. Jiva is the weak aspect because of instability caused by being affected by all thoughts, words and actions. Jiva (or Eve) is the part which

succumbs to temptation causing us to fall from the understanding of our true Self; the Atman. This fall is called 'sin' but it is neither good nor bad; it is the normal effect of being incarnated into a human body as against any other creature. Only embodied Atman in human beings is subjected to deviation or temptation. Only human beings suffer from mental deviations or desires.

The false understanding of the Adam and Eve text, is at the root of the denigration of the female gender. Eve is the weak side of all of us which gives way to the desires of the worldly life. When the RC church fathers formed their doctrine such statements as, "The woman is the Devil's gateway." Written by Tertullian who lived in the 2nd century, were formative in placing the female gender to be at fault. Tertullian was a defender of the new Christian religion when it was not recognised legally within Rome. Within his false idea Eve was seen as the one responsible for the "fall of man". Contrary to common belief this "fall" did not happen once in the history of mankind. It is happening every day due to the weakness of the human ego in both males and females. It is the Eve in all of us, both males and females, which cannot resist the pleasures of the worldly life. This 'Eve' does not have any gender. Men and women succumb to temptation equally. This is happening every single day; this one and only day.

Yet the false concept of the female gender being the weak one spiritually and responsible for the male gender falling into misdemeanours was firmly anchored into RC Christian theology from the very first centuries. These people did not understand scripture; or they deliberately altered the meanings.

Later, in 313 AD when the Roman Emperor Constantine accepted the Christian religion, the sidelining of the female gender gained strength. Constantine and his administrators were the architects of the whole structure of the Christian church which would go forward into the coming millennia. This did not include women in any important role; due to following the male dominated way the Roman Empire was governed. Hence the new religion would be male dominated from the start. This gave a new credence to the idea of Tertullian that women were to blame for man's misdemeanours; hence to be shunned. This created a stereotype for the female gender which still lives today.

This concept has come forward into the present time in the nations which do not allow women to show any part their body in public. The basis for this is that, if men see parts of the female body then they are tempted into harbouring sexual thoughts. It is thought that women cause these desires by showing attractive parts of their body. Yet the truth is that it is the weakness in the minds of men (Eve) which give rise to the sexual desires. Yet women are held to be the tempter; in the same way that the false idea of Eve has come to us from thousands of years of false understanding. The basic error of this idea means that the men do not see that they need to exercise control of their desires. Hence the problems surrounding men's sexual desires persist within societies, with women held as being the originators of this situation; and being forced to hide their bodies in public. To be truly human is to overcome animal desires.

I am not supporting the way that women flirt the shape of their bodies in public, in this 21st century. They chose to dress in such a way that men can see the form of their naked body with only a tight fitting thin layer of material to cover it. If this is worn to draw attention to their body or to attract other's eyes to their body, then it is clearly being seductive and is improper; call it evil if you like. I do not agree with women being dressed in this way, any more than I would support men being dressed like that; like ballet dancers sometimes do.

So to sum up this important part, we should now be clear that the RC organisation based part of its structure on the false belief that women are evil, because a non-existent physical Eve is falsely to blame for mankind giving-in to desires. Thus they fully justified the denigration of the female gender in any way which suited the male domination of their so-called church. None of this is based on the teachings of Jesus. The main questions are:- are they therefore followers of Jesus? Or are they followers only of their own organisation? Which was originally formed as a way to have control over the lives of all citizens of the Roman Empire. Were they correct to call this a religion? Or should it be called a political regime masquerading as religion?

China has a massive population of 1.4 billion, forced to believe state propaganda, does 1.4 billion make state propaganda correct and true. RC and its offshoots are now 2.6 billion people; this number of followers does not make the RC system truthful.

Such texts of Saul of Tarsus as:-

1. "Let a woman learn in silence with full submission. I permit no woman to teach or to have authority over a man; she is to keep silent" *1 Timothy 2:11-12*
2. "Women should be silent in the churches" *1 Corinthians 14:34-35*

These texts not only continue and enforce the accepted denigration of women at that time, they also beg the question, "**Was Saul (Paul) a follower of Jesus or a Jewish misogynistic reformer?**" Read all the teaching in his letters, and show me one passage of Jesus' teaching or one mention of Jesus' parables. Also there is no mention of Jesus miracles. It is clear he was what we now call, "a cult leader." More interested in gaining followers and in his own interpretation of Jewish scripture. Only one who is awake can see this in his writings.

He himself said in Romans 15:20, "*Yea, so I have strived to preach the gospel (his own), not where Christ was named, lest I should build upon another man's foundation.*" He always says, "my gospel" not that of Jesus. This is part of the RC legacy which still has its impact throughout Europe in this 21st Century.

It is my view that this man should never have been given the title "saint" neither should his teachings be placed in the same book as those of Jesus. This was another mistake by the original compilers of the Bible. But they were trying to keep everyone in the Roman Empire happy (except the women) so as to reduce the risk of dissent. So they included texts from all the main groups who were to be made to follow a new Roman religion. This is the reason why the Jewish books are with the ones about Jesus. Most people do not see this.

It is such things as a massive and ornate cathedral, as we have in the City of London, which put a powerful stamp onto the authority of a man who had no legitimate authority; only that which he made up himself, with the false account of the road to Damascus incident, used to claim his “**authority to act**”. All three accounts of this are different. Pointing to either or both, fake news or myth. Is this the mark of how the RC organisation based its foundation?

In the past members of the RC organisation were not allowed to research or to hold controversial views. Is this the reason why there are so many who blindly follow RC domination of their free right to worship in any way which suits the individual? What kind of legacy is that?

Amassing Wealth

In Matthew 19:23 and 24 Jesus raises the subject of material wealth as being a barrier to entry into the Kingdom of Heaven. The normal view is that this means God will not accept you at death of the body. Or I guess it means you cannot be truly Christian if you love wealth more than following the teaching of Jesus. These ideas may have some relevance. But let us adopt my previous interpretation of “Kingdom of Heaven is within you.” inferred by Jesus. That it is not a place somewhere else, but is part of our lives here and now.

This subject is not so much about wealth any more than other worldly matters which occupy the mind and cause worry, concern or stress. The Kingdom of Heaven can only be a state in life or of the mind. Even if we take it to mean a place where we will go after death, surely we expect it to be a state of bliss, care-free happiness in the mind. Yet Jesus indicated that it is not some place elsewhere, but is within us. Meaning it is within our capacity to live in peace and happiness at all times. The alternative is to be filled with worry, concern or stress. Speak to anyone who suffers from persistent mental stress problems and they will say such things as, “Life is Hell.” We choose stress or peace ourselves.

All spiritual teaching is about training the human mind to steer away from worldly attractions and to focus on the love of the Creator. It is only relevant to those people who have glimpsed that there is another side to human life; which is not tangled up with the mundane matters of the life in the physical body. For all other people it really serves little purpose other than giving them the opportunity to live less with animal instincts and to consider the well being of others with whom they come into contact.

Great teachers always speak in terms which their audience can relate to; hence, it maybe that the wealthy during Jesus’ time were those who were particularly stressed. The main part is more than likely the state of mind which carries the guilt of having so much more wealth than the average person. This guilt arises because the wealthy do not always become rich due entirely to their own efforts. In many cases it is poorly paid workers who create the wealth which the rich enjoy. Let me now tell a short story in this regard.

In the early 1940s my wife Anne was then a young schoolgirl. Anne had a friend whose family went to the RC church. On their way home one day Anne’s

friend said, "Will you help me with my collections?" Not knowing what it was, she agreed. The task was to knock on the doors of some of the poorest RC families in Leicester, where Anne lived. When they came to the door they were asked to pay their regular contribution to support the church. They were made to feel it was an obligation. Anne was appalled, she could not take part. This was either during or soon after the second world war. These families were starving due to lack of money; and the church knew this. Was this the teaching of Jesus? No! He taught the opposite of this. How large organisations mutate with time. Especially when changes will benefit them in the worldly way.

In the middle ages the church taxed all citizens 10% of their annual profits or production. Later abolished in the UK but still relevant in Germany today; about 9% is taken from all church members, protestant, RC and Jewish. The tax is levied at source by the state. This shows that RC and the others were not really a truly spiritual organisation from the beginning. They were nothing more than a disguised form of state control, taking taxes from the people.

Christianity was made the official religion by Theodosius in 380AD. All other religious sects were banned. Roman emperors were considered to be Gods, a concept transferred later to the RC religious leader called the Pope. All these factors are what formed the control system of religion in Europe; it was really about being wealthy and in control of the masses of people. Where is any teaching of Jesus which they can quote to give them the authority to do all this in His name - i.e. **Christ-ianity**.

This is the legacy which the power controlled RC organisation has given Europe and much of the world where Christian ideas are spread.

In India, where Jesus was taught much of His teaching, there is an established tradition with regard to money and spiritual teaching or training; it can be described as follows (from a holy man in India):-

"The spiritual teacher, who asks for money in return for spiritual training, steals the aspirant's property and will go to damnable hell. All great teachers have never taken money from their followers. They consider that if they do take money then the sins of the followers will be transferred to the teacher. It is considered that such knowledge and teaching is priceless and can never be sold for money. Whoever takes money for it insults it."

This was taught to me in India and most likely Jesus also knew this. It shows that the RC leaders and the others are storing up for themselves the most horrible karma (future life) which maybe in their current body or the next. This leads us on to the subject of reincarnation.

The One Life of the Soul

The current Christian teaching or doctrine is that the human being will go to one of two places when the body dies. The church cannot provide any evidence for this; also Jesus never taught this idea. In fact He taught that the soul has many bodies but one life. Evidence of this comes from an early Christian teacher named Origen of Alexandria; described as the greatest Christian author-

ity of all time. He lived near the end of the second century and the beginning of the third. He wrote:- *“Jesus taught that the soul originated in God and was returning to Him through the lessons of many incarnations.”* This sentence accords with all the important features of the most ancient and comprehensive philosophy on this planet – the scriptures of Vedanta. Jesus learned these in India. There is too much historic evidence that Jesus was in India for this to be refuted. Only those with the coloured vision contained within Palestine, will not wish to believe this. The book called, *“The Unknown Life of Jesus Christ.”* gives all the details you need. Also if you go to India and talk about Jesus, people will commonly refer to the time when He was there.

This concept of reincarnation was part of Christian doctrine until the sixth century. So for more than 500 years people who followed the so called Christian religion had the benefit of knowing that the long and difficult process of seeking closeness to the Creator did not have to be rushed in one lifetime. Also that it was their own individual business; not that of others or so called holy or celibate priests. Each person could shape their own spiritual life and practises.

There are other benefits of having the knowledge of reincarnation; such as understanding how inner tendencies or habits arise in life with no explanation as to where they came from. Hence the understanding that they were wrapped around the soul as seeds in the previous incarnation, and have re-germinated in the current life, is very helpful knowledge. Also the knowledge that previous bad karma can be eliminated by stronger and purer karma in this current life. But the main benefit is that a person comes to know that their future progress or regress is entirely within their own control. It is not the province of religious officials. Each of us is free to mould his/her own spiritual destiny.

It would seem this last benefit was behind the abolition of the knowledge of reincarnation. The emperor Justinian was what we would call today ‘a despot’. He saw himself as the supreme ruler of the empire and the pope of the church. Proving that the religion was only an extension of state control. Justinian taught that human life was only one body and that it was the established church (the state) who were the mediators of people’s salvation. Hence in his thinking the people were not in control of their own life through the concept of good karma. How many parts of the scriptures were erased or modified to suit the Romans we will never know. Research has shown scripture was changed greatly.

It was because the knowledge of reincarnation taught by Jesus and Origen was against the idea that the church (the state in disguise) was the only arbiter, that it had to be made into a heresy. Not only that, fake news about Origen and other fake teaching was provided as evidence that Origen was a heretic. This is an established manner of state leaders when they wish to put down opposition of another person assuming control of the state, which we see is a method well and truly alive in modern times. Henceforth from the sixth century Christians were not able to have the benefit of the knowledge of reincarnation. This is another legacy which all Christians live with today across the globe.

Pandemics and Medicine

This is the subject of community healers. History connects them with Pagan times as people with vast knowledge of cures derived from the chemistry of plants. Their origins are lost in the obscurity of the past. However, one thing is certain; due to their specialised and maybe secretive knowledge of plant based cures for many difficult human diseases; they were thought to be wielders of some kind of magic. The general public could only interpret the rapid and complete cure of long term sicknesses as being magical. This was confirmed in Europe when later knowledge of Jesus healing sick people of incurable diseases became known. He was thought to be a magical person. Community healers became known as witches or wise people with magic, living in the community; and because they cured people they were often called 'witches'. The real magic is Mother Nature's chemistry in plants. But the term "witch" had a range of meanings from beneficial to harmful. Many words in languages change their meanings radically due to the effects of the common use and their range of application. The English word "gay" was once commonly used for light hearted and happy not specifically a sexual terminology.

It is not difficult to see that when Europeans began studying the scriptures in the Bible, that they would come across the passage in Exodus 22:18 which says :- *"thou shalt not suffer a witch to live."* But this Old Testament word "witch" may not have been a beneficial person; hence came a turning point in the history of the community healers - or herbalists.

When the RC church had a major East - West schism it was a shock to the established system of bishops and pope. There seemed to be no cure for the split in doctrinal ideas which had crept up on them. After this they began a regime of "prevention is better than cure" to seek out where there might be dissent amongst the parishes across Europe. Hence the well documented "Inquisition" of the Catholic church. This installed a sense of panic, not only within the clergy but within the staunch and ardent followers of the faith; the parishioners. Everyone was on the look-out for people who spoke or did anything against the doctrine of the RC organisation. No one questioned whether the doctrine might be at fault (i.e. could have been the cause of the schism). Hence people known as magical healers or witches were suspected in many cases.

There is another subject in here. It is the strict RC rules about marriage and childbirth. Whereas before the time of RC controls there was not so much a stigma about pregnancy outside marriage, the new RC religious situation made it into a mortal sin. I have studied every verse of Jesus' teachings, as recorded; I cannot find any condemnation of such things. Also in John chapter 8, the incident of the lady accused of adultery (sex outside of marriage) Jesus was clear that He did not condemn her. So the RC policy on this is not Jesus' teaching. It comes from the Jewish Rabbis not their scriptures. Three or four hundred years before Jesus' time, these religious leaders forbade extra-marital sexual contact. So by Jesus' time it was well established. The RC system is basically Jewish.

If there was an RC stigma about this subject then we can be sure that contraception and causing abortion were included. Both of these are easy to deal with through the administration of herbal medicine. It only needed the word “witch” to be used by any outraged parishioner and the community healer would be in line for a death sentence.

Across Europe hundreds of thousands of innocent women, so called witches, were burnt on wooden stakes due to the panic of the RC administration of their “Inquisition” into anyone who said or did anything which might start the wild-fire of dissent. Thus in the 15th to 18th centuries many European communities were deprived of their community healers. During this time an unknown number of millions of people died of bubonic plague epidemics and other outbreaks of influenza like fevers. There are numerous herbal cures for these illnesses. But with less herbal knowledge in the community, many people died who could have lived. How ignorant of the religious leaders to “shoot the community in the foot” as it were.

Since those days herbalists have had a hard time getting their expertise accepted in European communities; due to the RC stigma of the so called witches. This is more so in the UK in the 21st century. Here we have another legacy from the RC way of doing things.

Celibacy and Sexuality

There is nothing in Jesus’ teaching which suggests that His followers should refrain from marriage or normal sexual activities. Hence celibacy was not a requirement of following Jesus’ teachings. When Jesus said to Mary Magdalena, “Go and sin no more.” This indicates that He listed sexuality for pleasure as a sin; or a thing that should not be done. At the turn of the 10th century within the RC church it was discovered that the sexual abuse of boys by priests was out of control. This created a crisis within the administration of the RC church. Sexual abuse matters were quite naturally covered up, as sexual things were generally private and no-one wanted to speak of them. Also an organisation promoting good behaviour (the RC) should not be seen to condone such sins; therefore it was covered up. Hence this matter took nearly a century to solve. The outcome was that around 1139 at the second lateral council of the RC church, all priests were required to be celibate. This was thought to be a cure for priests behaving sexually towards both children and married women within the parish. But in fact it was this imposed celibacy which made the situation worse. No-one can impose celibacy on another. It must be free personal choice. Otherwise it leads to huge sexual frustration.

Inner spiritual development is a matter of taking full control of the human mind. It is the mind which is really the Devil in us. If the mind is not under control there can truly be no deep inner contemplation of the oneness of the Creator; which is what leads to union with Him. Sexual thinking is surely the strongest urge in mankind generally. It can also be one of the greatest distractions for the mind. It is for this reason celibacy is recommended for those who

wish to embrace the last stage of spiritual progress; for both males and females. This idea of celibacy does not have to be life-long. Which means it can be embraced later in married life when the sexual urge has naturally abated. Also it cannot be imposed on a person by anyone else; it must be a matter of personal choice. But celibacy here means mainly controlling the desires and the thoughts about sexual matters; control of the mind. If there is physical abstinence, but the aspirant still has imaginings and desires for sexual activities, then it is not celibacy, because the mind has not been brought under control. Thoughts about any subject usually precede the physical enactment of that subject. This is how we instigate all activities as human beings.

The above is the reason for the RC failure to understand that requiring a person to abstain from sexual matters before he or she has controlled the desires, will lead to mental sexual frustration. Hence sexual abuse of those people who trust the 'celibate' priest is inevitable. Such abuse has occurred in large numbers during all those centuries since celibacy was made compulsory. The RC church has made no attempt to connect the celibacy requirement with the increase in abuse; hence they are unable to control it. In history even Popes have been involved in cases of this kind of abuse. It has all been either covered up or explained away. It is as if the RC organisation has no wish to talk about the subject.

The affect on the victims has an intensity like no other kind of abuse. It is because priests are supposed to be representatives of the God that RC followers believe in, that the victims find themselves unable to be free of the effects or to understand how it could happen to them. Many victims suffer for several decades with multiple trauma effects in their lives. The fact that an organisation, into which they have entrusted their soul, has created such stress and confusion, means therapists cannot untangle the complexities of it.

In previous centuries in Ireland, young RC girls who became pregnant before marriage, were taken from their families and put into a kind of RC prison environment, called "Mother and Baby Institutions" (M&BI). There they were deprived of their babies; a dreadful thing to do to a young mother and to the baby. The girls were made to work like slaves. Also because the male members of the RC organisation realised that these girls were not virgins, they were all seriously abused sexually. How can we call the priests Christians? This abuse of young girls by so called celibate religious people was fully exposed in the 20th century. Also there is serious doubt about what happened to their babies.

A discovery this century in Tuan, County Galway, Ireland, has revealed that more than 9,000 young children 'died' in eighteen of the M&BI's across Ireland. The deaths were not formally registered and their bodies were disposed of in old sewage chambers. There was no Christian burial of these children. Their deaths were covered up by the Catholic Church, who has admitted the offences and paid £millions in costs and compensation to the families involved.

We need to think about the reasons for not declaring the deaths of these small children. Were they poorly fed, neglected or murdered? Will we ever know? This was clearly not the actions of a truly religious organisation.

The above abuses by religious people has occurred across the globe with both girls and boys; the perpetrators have been shielded, the victims ignored and the offences covered up. There have been hundreds of thousands of victims across the world; who often are so confused, ashamed and affected that the abuse does not surface until decades after; allowing the perpetrators to escape conviction. The whole RC church and all its protestant and other forms are guilty of this.

In this 21st century there has been unprecedented occurrences of this kind of abuse of boys and girls. Such is the cover up, by even those at the top, that the Archbishop (the pope of) the Anglican Church had to resign in 2024 due to his inaction about many cases he knew about. It was as if he thought, "If I leave it long enough it will go away." It seems he did not know or care about the seriousness of the effect on the victims. Not truly Christian actions. This is another lasting legacy of the RC and the other so called religious organisations on the societies across the world.

Are all these people really following the teachings of Jesus? Are they truly followers of Jesus?

Understanding the Spiritual Path

The quote of Origen's words, "*Jesus taught that the soul originated in God and was returning to Him through the lessons of many incarnations.*" is a brief understanding of the basic nature of the spiritual path. It is an understanding that the being within us, the one which is conscious of all that happens, is a small part of the Creator; i.e. "originated in". This which we call "myself" believes it was separated from Him at some time in the past. This also means that the Creator is aware of all that is happening in our lives; because in this view, our consciousness is part of His consciousness. All spiritual and religious teaching aims at understanding this fact. i.e. "The Kingdom of Heaven is within you."

Yet as I have said earlier, human beings do have a difficulty in understanding the allegory within Holy Scripture; the example was of the story of Adam and Eve being a description of the strong and weak parts within all of us. Such words spoken or written down come from a human being; mostly one who has reached the goal of the spiritual path mentioned above; hence knows what the words intend. Thus the words are for the purpose of guiding people who may wish to embark on the spiritual path mentioned above. Called in many ways:- "the realisation of the true nature of the Self within."

Misunderstanding of the words of holy people as mentioned above is recorded in the New Testament, as follows, spoken by John or Jesus about His 'so called' disciples :-

"Therefore speak I to them in parables: because they seeing see not; and hearing they hear not, neither do they understand." Matt. 13:3

"Are ye also yet without understanding?" Matt. 15:16

"Why do ye not understand my speech? (is it) even because ye cannot hear my word." John 8:43

"And they understood none of these things: and this saying was hid from them, neither knew they the things which were spoken." Luke 18:34

The difficulty holy teachers have is the above ignorant state of their audience. To tell people directly to their face that they are living their lives incorrectly, or that they have evil in their minds, will not be received happily by the average person. Hence analogy is needed, as in the Adam and Eve story along with the Satan or Devil allegory. When human society does not have teachers who understand the purpose and function of scriptural analogy, then the mind of the religious leaders will misinterpret the meanings behind the words. It is with this error the RC organisation was built from the very beginning.

To create the idea of a fictitious being who is evil and will lead people astray, is one way of getting people to focus on the evil in themselves and to think to correct it. Especially if this fabricated being is said to be living within people and is misguiding them. Hence the analogy of the so called being of the Devil or Satan is not about an actual being. In truth there is no such being other than the human mind itself. There really is only one thing to do on the spiritual path; it is to correct and purify the human mind and take it away from its unnecessary focus on the imagined importance of worldly issues.

This "realisation" mentioned above cannot happen when the mind is "impure". This word "impure" does not mean evil or bad, it is the natural state of the mind focussed on the world and the daily tasks. Mind becomes very attached to the world through such things as desire for pleasure, desire for wealth or desire for fame or popularity. These desires can become so strongly established in a person's life that it becomes a lifetime's task to weaken or remove them. Thus removed, the mind will become purified, in this spiritual sense. This event of purification has never been known to happen en-mass as it were; dozens or hundreds of people becoming mentally purified at the same time, has not been recorded in history. Instead we have many references to individuals becoming "God realised" or "Self realised"; which are both the same thing. It is a permanent 'state of being', once done cannot be undone. Hence it is not an experience which happens one day and then life goes back to normal when the experience fades in the memory. This is what Jesus meant when He said "---- the power to become sons of God." (John 1) You will know it every day.

This process of individuals progressing by their own effort and finding communion with the Creator within their own experience of life, is anathema to those people who wish to use spiritual teaching as a means to control the behaviour of the masses of people in a large society; in a city or an empire controlled by an Emperor. Hence all religious ways which seek any form of public control

will not interpret the teachings of the holy ones such that individuals have their own relation to the teaching or their own relation with the Creator. This leads to what we see in the western or European forms which religion has taken; where self appointed leaders tell the people how to worship and what the scriptures mean. It is a semi-political use of spiritual teaching devised by the community leaders to support their own ideas of control of the population. This way of promoting Jesus' teachings is behind the wrongful interpretation of His words which have been mentioned above. Hence, truly understanding the spiritual path has these obstacles.

The way the RC system was designed is a powerful legacy of the above kind which has become so strongly established that this paper will be difficult for many readers to get into its real meanings. You may need to absorb its content, reflect on it and read it many times.

Gathering People in a Single Building

Western people think that Indian temples are an equivalent to the church, mosque, synagogue or temple of the western style of doing things. This is a natural error of mental projection; seeing a thing in a way that the imagination is happy or familiar with it, so that there is not a new thing to be understood. This western view of Indian temples is entirely false.

There is no community gathering in an Indian temple as with churches, mosques or synagogues. The western way of so called community worship is not what Jesus taught; large numbers gathering in a single building to pray. This statement will come as a surprise to many people. But it is actually the teaching of Jesus to **not** do that thing of gathering together in large groups.

It is recorded in the Gospel of Matthew Chpt 6 vv 5&6 that Jesus taught:-

“And when thou prayest, thou shalt not be as the hypocrites are: for they love to pray standing in the synagogues and in the corners of the streets, that they may be seen of men. Verily I say unto you, they have their reward.

“But thou, when thou prayest, enter into thy closet, and when thou hast shut thy door, pray to thy Father which is in secret; and thy Father which seeth in secret shall reward thee openly.”

This accords with the previous section where each individual needs to make that communication with the Creator, alone as a one to one experience. Also it is the way prayer and worship is carried out in Indian homes & temples, which Jesus would have seen in many places during His 30 or more years in India.

But the RC system in the beginning was nothing more than another form of Judaism where their churches were called synagogues. Hence Jesus' use of that word means the same as church or mosque; religions which evolved out of Judaism. Hence when the RC religion was formulated they could not envisage any other way of worship. And they completely ignored, or misinterpreted, the above clear and unequivocal teaching of Jesus.

This ignoring or misinterpretation of key teaching by Jesus has led to the construction of many huge buildings at great expense and effort by the commu-

nities. It is always large buildings which make a statement about all things political or where people control is the main subject. Hence we have large government buildings in all countries; and where religions seek to create a people governing function, they too have large buildings. It is the effect of such large buildings which span many generations and are at the root of giving legitimacy to fake or false ways of religious organisations. There are many cult like semi-religious organisations in the USA which seek to control people's lives and take their money. All of them seek to establish legitimacy through having large buildings.

Eileen Barker was commissioned in the 1980s by the UK government to research problems with the rise of "new religious movements" or secretive cults. She established a list of common characteristics which defined them as being cult like; 'cult' meaning then, "an organisation which sought to take control of people's lives and divest them of their individuality". When she was in the process of recommending whether or not these organisations should be outlawed under British law, it came to her attention that the various forms of the Christian church fitted the list of cult characteristics almost exactly. Hence the wording of any legislation enacting control of the cults, would have to apply to the RC church and others; for that reason outlawing 'cults' became inadvisable. This actually told her a lot about how religion worked in the UK.

This shows that when all things religious are examined in a fully academic way, that they mostly have the same aim; to take over control of how people relate to higher things.

Here is the most wide sweeping legacy we have from the RC organisation; and why it is I have used the term "organisation" in many places in preference to the term "religion".

Summary

Here we have a mixed bag of legacies from the organisation which adopted the Roman idea of belief in a higher being or beings. This belief system was itself modelled on the belief system of the Greeks. There is no doubt that the architecture of the RC organisation began in Rome and was formed or guided by Roman people. This is historically recorded. It was a huge leap for the Romans to part with their concept of many gods and to adopt the Jewish idea of a single God of the whole world.

In the established ancient Roman Pagan idea they had higher beings, worship, prayer and daily practises. So their belief system was meant to be part of every day; here and now in this one day. Over previous centuries the Romans had built their empire by accepting the deities of other systems and the deities of those people they conquered. But the new Roman belief system was to be followed according to state decree. There was no real individual choice in the matter. Hence when the ideas of the Jews and the Christian Jews (followers of Paul) were adopted, new teaching may have been embraced, but who controlled it did not change. This means what has been believed to be the adoption of Christian-

ity in Rome did not include freedom of choice. It was by state decree that all other belief systems were stopped and one system was made compulsory.

Due to the difficulties in understanding profound teaching detailed above, the spiritually ignorant leaders were not capable of making the system embrace the true principles of Jesus' teachings. Hence the RC system developed in the way that it did. The diverse ways in which this was eventually practised across the whole Roman Empire was regulated by various councils, held in various locations across the centuries. This shows that it was really like a political system decided by majority ecclesiastical voting. It has left us with both a positive and negative legacy.

RC type Christians do not understand why the Jewish scriptures are included in the same book as Jesus' teachings. However, they do think that they should follow the ten commandments of Moses. Let's see how the above legacy has scored with these ten.

1. No other gods - they mostly worship the Pope as if he is God. This is another God in the view of the Old Testament.
2. Make no images - this can relate to imaginations in the mind. Worshiping matters of the material world when the mind imagines about them.
3. The name of God in vain. The appalling slaughter of both so called heretics and witches in the name of God, was such a thing. Jesus did not teach killing miscreants. Instead He forgave them.
4. Keep one day Holy - they did this alright.
5. Honour father and mother. These are the first teachers in your life, so it infers honouring all your teachers. Not following Jesus' teaching as He spoke it, is not honouring Him.
6. Shall not kill. Killing 'so called' heretics and witches breached this rule.
7. Not commit adultery - the sexual abuse of boys, girls and parishioner's wives definitely counts as adultery.
8. Shall not steal. Charging (taxes) for religion, especially to the poor, is theft.
9. False witness. Not telling, or concealing the true story of Jesus' life is lying.
10. Not coveting other's possessions. The church is the biggest land and property owner in Europe. Not sure if that is coveting. Seems like it.

Possibly a score of one and two halves out of ten. 20% is not a pass mark.

Apart from the poor performance and the serious legacy outlined above, the promoting of the Gospels of Jesus' teaching was the best thing that the RC organisation facilitated. But as mentioned above, it was not their intention that everyone should have access to that teaching, it was for the priests and bishops etc. to use as control weapons for the people in general. But time changes all things as I said above. And the advent of the printing press was a good thing for all those people who wanted to read Jesus' teaching for themselves. Albeit we all had to wait 1,400 years for that to happen. Then people could do what Jesus wanted them to do. Study His teachings and live their life by them.

If, from the beginning, the RC Romans had set up schools to teach people to read, for those who wanted to read the teaching; then simply made the scriptures available to all for study; they need not have become involved in running a large organisation. Thus avoiding all the risks of corruption, abuse, mismanagement and false doctrines which that entailed. But allowing the general population to have control of their own spiritual life was not part of the Roman way at the time.

So we have a two part legacy; this is the double edged sword mentioned in the preface. The many serious effects on society outlined above; and eventually after a long wait, the benefit to all from reading part of the teachings of Jesus and individually making a life from His advice.

The Kingdom of Heaven is Within You

The beauty you see in the world comes from Him who exists within you.
Without His presence within, you would not see anything, even that beauty.

First know that your-Self is Him, then no one thing will seem to be more beautiful than any other thing. You will know that He is all things.

Then you have true Self-knowledge. This is the purpose of your life.
When you have finished with the worldly things, don't forget to remember yourself, and to forget the world. Otherwise in the end your life is truly empty.

To make your life full, study the scriptures which teach the above truth of life.

Have faith and trust that their knowledge will give you eternal peace.

Swami Vishnu Ananda Saraswati